

4onse: analysis of Four times Open Non-conventional system for Sensing the Environment

Experimental monitoring system deployment report

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For more information on the project 4nse, link to <http://www.4nse.ch>

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Executive summary

This report elaborates the deployment of 4nse experimental monitoring system in Deduru Oya basin and other several locations in Sri Lanka. Twenty seven (27) systems have been installed in the Deduru Oya basin – out of them, 15 are MOD (Modular version) stations and 12 are PCB (Printed Circuit Board version) stations. Two (02) PCB systems have been installed outside the Deduru Oya basin at two different climatic zones. For testing purposes, three (03) systems (01 MOD station and 02 PCB stations) have been installed in the university premises. In addition, six (06) river gauges have been deployed in Deduru Oya river basin.

1 Introduction

The main objective of 4nse research project is, setting up a fully accessible, royalty free and low-cost environmental monitoring system based on open hardware, software, data and standards. The selected case study area to deploy the systems is Deduru Oya basin, which is the fourth largest river basin of Sri Lanka.

2 Case study area

The Deduru Oya is 115km long and covers 2687km² of catchment area. It is located within the highly vulnerable areas due to climate change according to recent studies (Katupotha, 2009). As illustrated in Figure 1, the basin area falls under two climatic zones, wet and intermediate. 97% of the basin area is covered by the North Western Province (Kurunegala and Puttalam Districts) and 3% by the Central Province (Kandy and Matale Districts).

The rainfall in the basin has a significant temporal and spatial variation. Annual rainfall ranges from 2600mm in the upper basin to 1100mm in the lower basin. From the annual rainfall about 50% is received during inter monsoon months (March-April & October-November), about 35% during Southwest monsoon months (May to September), and remaining 15% during Northeast monsoon months (December to February) (Sampath, et.al, 2015). Presently, it releases nearly 1600 MCM of water to the sea annually (Environmental Impact Assessment Report, 2003). The Deduru Oya River carries flash floods during rainy season and very low flow during dry season. The very

Figure 1: Location of Deduru Oya basin

River carries flash floods during rainy season and very low flow during dry season. The very

low catchment gradient of the main stream which is about 0.0089, cause to create rapid floods in the downstream areas. There are 8 major reservoirs and 2408 minor reservoirs in the basin (Figure 2). Deduru Oya reservoir is the largest reservoir / tank in the basin which has a capacity of 75,000,000m³.

Figure 2 - Deduru oya basin and its major reservoirs

Source: Irrigation Department, Sri Lanka

3 The existing hydrometeorological network and decision-making setup of Sri Lanka

The hydrometeorological network is the key requirement for most hydrological forecasting. However, most developing countries lack weather observing networks that routinely provide data of the necessary quality, and spatial and temporal density. Since they do not have comprehensive weather observing networks, most of the time they have to rely on forecast information provided by developed nations via the global telecommunications network. Just as in developed countries, developing countries need weather observing networks to accomplish their missions: meeting the local needs for warning of severe weather, promoting economic growth, and supporting the activities of their nation's citizenry. The commonly found challenges has been identified in a limited (often very limited) budgets, and the lack of technical infrastructure and associated expertise, rapid deterioration, lack of skilled maintenance, high-priced non-locally available spare parts (Snow, 2013).

Similarly, in Sri Lanka, the hydro-meteorological network coverage is restricted to certain locations of the country due to high installation and maintenance costs. Currently, water resources data and meteorological data pertaining to river basins are collected by five government agencies according to their own protocols. They are, Irrigation Department for hydro-meteorological data, Central Environmental Authority for water quality data, National Water Supply and Drainage Board and the Water Resources Board for groundwater data and

Meteorological Department for Climate data. There is no cooperative arrangement among these agencies for sharing the data. Hence, still there is no central water database being developed for Sri Lanka where all the data are brought together and integrated. The national hydrological archives mostly retained as hard copies. Since the data is not freely and publicly available and non-interoperable, every time, the researchers and decision makers need to purchase data and required to undergo redundant data collection procedures.

Most of the weather stations in Sri Lanka are manually operated and data is transmitted vocally over the phone. In addition, Meteorological Department owns several Automated Weather Stations (AWS) which were installed using funds from international organizations. Rainfall, Temperature, Pressure, Humidity, Wind speed and direction, Solar Radiation and Humidity are the parameters measured by the AWSs. Due to the high purchasing and maintenance cost, only 37 AWSs have been installed at regional Meteorological stations and Collaborative stations. Most of the time, the hardware of software of these stations cannot be adjusted to integrate new parameters (Senevirathna, S. and Jayawickrama, V., 2014). Therefore, there are certain gaps pertaining to data accuracy, completeness, consistency, timeliness and coverage.

The existing hydro-meteorological network of Deduru Oya river basin consists of several stations belong to Meteorological Department and Irrigation Department. In addition, the Bathalagoda rice research institute has certain weather monitoring devices at their premises. As depicted in Figure 3, one (01) regional station of Meteorological Department located inside the basin and the other four (04) nearby regional stations are located outside the basin. The Irrigation Department owns three (03) rain gauges and three (03) river gauges in the basin area. These regional stations of Meteorological Department collect parameters related to rainfall, temperature and relative humidity on daily basis and the parameters related to solar radiation and wind speed are collected on monthly and annual basis respectively. The data is not freely available, and some data are still available in hard copy format. Table 1.0 shows the usual rates imposed by the Meteorological Department for different parameters.

Figure 3: Hydrometeorological stations belong to government organizations

Table 1: Rates imposed by the Meteorological Department

Parameter	Available Interval	Rate per month per station (LKR)
Rainfall	daily	40.00
Temperature (Min & Max)	daily	80.00
Relative humidity	daily	80.00
Solar radiation	monthly	600.00
Wind speed	annually	70.00 (rate per annum)

4 The approach of selecting suitable locations for the 4nse systems

4.1 Theoretical background

The two major questions that arise in deploying weather station networks are: (1) What is the minimum number of stations required? (2) Where should the stations be located? The answers for these two questions depend on the particular application – parameters being measured, topography, budgetary and personnel constraints, purpose of the stations, availability of telecommunication facilities and other special needs.

Although World Meteorological Organization (WMO) recommends minimum rain gauge station densities (Table 2) for different physiographic areas with some detailed standards on siting and calibrating the instruments used in the stations, there is no standard guideline on identifying the number and the ideal locations to deploy them. Since the parameters like precipitation and wind speed can vary greatly with small distances, in reality, the required density is higher than the recommended density by the WMO. The necessity of a higher network density arises as a result of the rate of variation of observed parameters across an area. A sparse network is sufficient to measure surface temperature, a fairly dense network to measure maximum and minimum temperature and very dense network to examine precipitation and wind (WMO, 2011). Out of them, precipitation is the main source of water input that falls from the atmosphere as rain, snow, freezing rain, sleet and hail. Moreover, precipitation can vary greatly with small distances, especially in the tropical countries like Sri Lanka.

Table 2: Recommended minimum densities of rain gauge stations (area in km² per station)

Physiographic unit	Area in km ² per station	
	Non-recording	Recording
Coastal	900	9000
Mountains	250	2500
Interior plains	575	5750
Hilly/undulating	575	5750
Small islands	25	250
Urban areas	-	10 - 20
Polar / arid	10,000	100,000

Source: WMO, 2008

The topography of the area significantly influence on climate – temperature decreases with elevation, mountains force incoming wind to rise and make precipitation on the windward side by forming clouds, while causing the leeward side of the mountain to be dry, slopes of different

inclination and orientation receive different amount of solar energy. These diversified environmental processes create dissimilar microclimatic environments within a single mountainous region. Hence, the required network density for mountainous environments is comparatively higher than the areas with uniform terrain.

Several methods can be found in the literature, when deploying weather station networks. The most popular method is aimed at finding optimal sensor node deployment to minimize total energy spent in the network, while maximizing the connectivity. Voronoi approach (Ab Aziz, et.al, 2009; So and Ye, 2005; Viera, et.al, 2003; Fan and Biagioni, 2004; Sung and Yang, 2014), Particle Swarm Optimization algorithm (Kulkarni and Venayagamoorthy, 2011; Bennani and El Ghanami, 2012; Yang, et.al, 2016; Azharuddin and Jana, 2016) and Genetic algorithm (Zhang, et.al, 2008; Jourdan and de Weck, 2004; Yoon and Kim, 2013; Lai, et.al, 2007; Seo, et.al, 2009) are some of the most widely used approaches in this regard. However, unlike in the past when Automated Weather Stations (AWS) are placed where the electricity lines and telecommunication network is available, nowadays the technological advancements in renewable electricity generation technologies and cellular communication technologies have let AWSs to operate without directly connected to the electricity grid or telecommunication network. Therefore, site selection, primarily based on availability of electricity and telecommunication network is not a necessity for sensor networks operating nowadays.

The second approach is concerned with investigating the adequacy of the existing network and deciding some new locations for the weather stations based on the measurements of the existing stations using Geostatistical tools such as Kriging and Shannon's entropy method (Awadallah, 2012; Chen, et.al, 2008; Moulin, et.al, 2008; Karimi-Hosseini, et.al, 2011; Yeh, et.al, 2011). By placing stations in the higher entropy areas, the overall variance in precipitation, for example can be reduced. The limitation in this method is it requires precipitation measurements of the stations already exist on the basin. Therefore, the most challenging task is to find the optimum locations for sensor networks in an ungauged river basin where the measurements related to meteorological parameters are too cost, too few, too poor in quality or not available at all.

4.2 Methodology and results

The location identification for the 4nse systems was commenced under the constraint of no prior information on hydrometeorological condition and setting of the river basin is available.

As the foremost step, the boundary and the sub-basins of the watershed were delineated using the SWAT hydrological modelling tool. A total of 22 sub-basins were received for the Deduru Oya watershed (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Delineated sub-basins of Deduru Oya watershed.

The locations of the 4nse systems were primarily decided based on the rainfall. The rainfall data required for this study was obtained from National Centers for Environmental Prediction (NCEP) Climate Forecast System Reanalysis (CFSR) database for the period of 2000 to 2013. The CFSR data set is the result of the close cooperation between two US organizations, the National Centers for Environmental Prediction (NCEP) and the National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR). It includes global climate data over 36 years (1979 – 2014).

Climate Forecast System Reanalysis (CFSR) database for the period of 2000 to 2013. Kriging geostatistical method (Equation 1) was applied to find the spatial distribution of average monthly rainfall over the area. Accordingly, 168 Kriging layers were produced which represent average monthly rainfall during the period of 2000 – 2013.

$$\hat{Z}(s_0) = \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i Z(s_i) \text{ Equation 1}$$

Where, $Z(s_i)$ is the measured value at the i^{th} location, λ_i is an unknown weight for the measured value at the i^{th} location, s_0 is the prediction location and N is the number of measured values.

Then the Shannon's entropy was applied to measure the uncertainty / disorder of rainfall distribution. In information theory, entropy is defined as the quantity of information possessed by a signal (Shannon, 1949). Koutsoyiannis (2005) defined entropy as "a measure of the amount of chaos" or "of the lack of information about the system". The quantity of information can be measured indirectly based on the degree of the reduction of uncertainty (Lee, 2013). Larger entropy means greater the uncertainty / disorder. Accordingly, the Shannon entropy of a discrete random variable x with N possible outcomes can be calculated as:

$$H_x = -\sum_{i=1}^N p(x_i) \cdot \log_{base} p(x_i) \text{ Equation 2}$$

Larger the entropy means greater the lack of information about the rainfall measurements. To calculate the pixel wise probabilities of occurrence of rainfall, all the Kriging layers were classified according to the scale below in Table 3.

Table 3: Classification scale of Kriging layers

Rainfall (mm)	range	Weight
0-50		1
50-100		2
100-150		3
150-200		4
200-250		5
250-300		6
300-350		7
350-400		8
400-450		9
450-500		10
500<		11

Finally, the raster analysis was performed to calculate the entropy values of each pixel. Figure 5 shows entropy values of some selected basins. The next task was to identify the best location out of the areas which have high entropy values.

When applying any meteorological data for hydrological modelling, most of the hydrological models consider the sub-basin level as the primary discretization scheme for a watershed. They take input data from the nearest station to its centroid. Therefore, high entropy value areas which located closer to the sub-basin's centroids were also considered as a priority factor.

In addition, several other factors were also considered in identifying suitable locations for the 4nse systems. Accordingly, the number and the final locations for the 4nse systems were decided based on the following things:

- Consideration of areas with high rainfall entropy
- Deploy at least one 4nse system in each sub-basin
- Proximity to sub-basin's centroid
- Accessibility – availability of road network to reach to the stations
- Signal strength

- Security – government or public places with security officers, less or no vulnerability for natural disasters
- Availability of open spaces
- More than 100m away from water bodies
- Areas with no effects from shadows of buildings and trees (when sun is higher than 5°)
- Availability of flat land
- Extent of the sub-basins - it was decided to install more than one station for sub-basins greater than 2 hectares

However, several locations were selected while disobeying the aforementioned criteria. They are:

- The extent of sub-basin 9 is less than 2 hectares. However, it was decided to install one more station at the upper area of the sub-basin 9 where the Deduru Oya stream is originated.
- It was decided not to install any station in sub-basin 15, due to the location of two nearby stations at sub-basin 9 and 16, within less than 5km distance.
- Upon the request of Irrigation Department two stations have been installed closer to two tanks called Hakwatuna and Kimbulwana and one more station has been installed at the Dam of Deduru Oya reservoir

The Figure 6 shows locations selected in Deduru Oya basin to deploy the 4nse systems as per the above methodology.

Figure 5: Selected location for 4ONSE systems, Entropy values and Subbasins' centroids of some subbasins in Deduru Oya River Basin

Figure 6: Locations of the 4onse weather stations in Deduru Oya basin

5 Details of the locations selected to deploy the 4nse systems

5.1 Weather stations deployed at Deduru Oya basin

As shown in Figure 6, twenty-seven (27) 4nse stations have been installed in the Deduru Oya basin. These stations can measure rainfall, temperature, pressure, relative humidity, solar radiation, wind speed, wind direction and soil moisture. Table 4 shows the type, sub-basin number, coordinates and the date of installation of the respective station numbered in Figure 6. The technical sheets pertaining to each station have been attached separately.

Table 4: Information of the 4nse weather stations installed at Deduru Oya basin

No	Name of the location	System Type	Location type	Sub-basin Number	Coordinates	Date of installation
01	Sri Sudarshanaramaya	MOD	Temple	01	7.77609, 80.10723	23.03.2018
02	Maeliya Maha Vidyalaya	PCB	School	12	7.74501, 80.4189	21.07.2018
03	Polpithigama Central College	MOD	School	12	7.81619, 80.40497	28.03.2018
04	Hakwatuna Irrigation Office	PCB	Irrigation Department's premises	02	7.77067, 80.44662	21.07.2018
05	Gunapala Malasekara Model Primary school	MOD	School	03	7.79459, 80.28381	23.03.2018
06	Bakmeegahawatta College	PCB	School	03	7.85393, 80.30532	21.07.2018
07	Hulogedara Maha Vidyalaya	MOD	School	04	7.79054, 80.19073	23.03.2018
08	Bamunugama Maha Vidyalaya	MOD	School	08	7.65746, 80.16155	06.03.2018
09	Kubukgete Central College	MOD	School	14	7.67338, 80.41995	28.03.2018

10	Medamulla De Mel Maha Vidyalaya	MOD	School	06	7.64323, 80.5093	28.03.2018
11	Kimbulwanawewa Irrigation Office	PCB	Irrigation Department's premises	09	7.64871, 80.47782	21.07.2018
12	Dodamgaslanda John Kothalawala Central College	MOD	School	07	7.56845, 80.53221	28.03.2018
13	Kedapathwehera Primary School	PCB	School	08	7.54703, 80.2529	06.03.2018
14	Hettipola Mahindodaya Maha Vidyalaya	PCB	School	08	7.60583, 80.07815	06.03.2018
15	Rambadagalla Central College	PCB	School	09	7.50758, 80.50921	14.07.2018
16	Wewala Parakrama Kanishta Vidyalaya	PCB	School	09	7.39998, 80.55304	14.07.2018
17	Paragahadeniya National School	PCB	School	11	7.41561, 80.47272	14.07.2018
18	Lyceum adventure park	MOD	Park belongs to Lyceum international school	10	7.45965, 80.36421	28.03.2019
19	Bathalagoda Rice Research Institute	MOD	Research institute	16	7.53148, 80.43538	16.03.2018
20	Porapola Kanishta Vidyalaya	PCB	School	16	7.59081, 80.35303	06.07.2018
21	S.B. Herath National School	MOD	School	16	7.65528, 80.34604	23.03.2018
22	Dam of Deduru Oya reservoir	PCB	Irrigation Department	18	7.71934, 80.27471	06.07.2018

			ent's premises			
23	Malagane Maha Vidyalaya	MOD	School	18	7.66651, 80.27807	23.03.2018
24	Gajanaggegama Maha Vidyalaya	MOD	School	19	7.73613, 80.24267	23.03.2018
25	Withikuliya Central College	MOD	School	20	7.71783, 80.14575	16.03.2018
26	Wellangiriya Govipola	PCB	Farm	21	7.68275, 79.97235	06.07.2018
27	Kokkawila Kanishta Vidyalaya	MOD	School	22	7.59464, 79.88334	06.03.2018

5.2 Weather stations deployed outside the Deduru Oya basin

Upon the request of United Nations Development Program (UNDP), two (02) weather stations have been installed at Lankapura and Walapane Divisional Secretariat areas. In addition, three (03) weather stations (02 PCB stations and 01 MOD station) have been installed in the University premises for testing purposes. The technical sheets pertaining to each station have been attached separately.

Table 5: Information of the 4nse weather stations installed outside the Deduru Oya basin

No	Name of the location	System Type	Location type	Coordinates	Date of installation
01	Lankapura	PCB	Divisional Secretariat Office	8.0319, 81.0334	29.09.2018
02	Walapane	PCB	Divisional Secretariat Office	7.0757, 80.8913	15.03.2019
03	Department of Town & Country Planning	PCB	Department of Town & Country Planning, University	6.7951, 79.9015	10.07.2018

			of Moratuwa			
04	Department Information Technology	of	PCB	Departmen t of Informatio n Technolog y, University of Moratuwa	6.7969, 79.9018	09.07.2018
05	Department Information Technology	of	MOD	Departmen t of Informatio n Technolog y, University of Moratuwa	6.7969, 79.9018	24.11.2018

5.3 River gauges deployed in Deduru Oya basin

Other than twenty seven (27) weather stations, six (06) river gauges have been installed at the Deduru Oya basin to measure the water level. Out of the six (06) river gauges, five (05) of them were installed in the upper basin area and the remaining one was installed at the lower basin closer to the Deduru Oya reservoir. Figure 7 shows the locations of all the river gauges and Table 6 shows information about respective river gauge numbered in Figure 7.

The upper basin of Deduru Oya watershed consists of four (04) streams namely Maguru Oya, Deduru Oya, Kimbulwana Oya and Hakwatuna Oya. These four (04) streams merged at the Deduru Oya reservoir, which is located at the center of the basin. 4onse river gauges were installed for each of the aforementioned streams to measure stream water level. Since Deduru Oya stream has the largest inflow, one more river gauge was installed at the upper part of the Deduru Oya stream. Apart from that, one river gauge was installed at the Ridie Bandi Ella anicut where the water is released to lower basin from the Deduru Oya reservoir. The technical sheets pertaining to each station have been attached separately.

Figure 7: Locations of the 4onse river gauges in Deduru Oya basin

Table 6: Information of the 4nse river gauges installed in the Deduru Oya basin

	Name of the location	Location type	Name of the stream	Coordinates	Date of installation
01	Maspotha	Bridge	Maguru Oya	7.54687, 80.30708	22.02.2019
02	Amunugama	Bridge	Deduru Oya	7.64433, 80.32288	21.03.2019
03	Deegama	Bridge	Kimbulwana Oya	7.67834, 80.37039	07.03.2019
04	Moragoda	Anicut	Hakwatuna Oya	7.74578, 80.34725	22.11.2018
05	Ridie Bandi Ella	Anicut	Deduru Oya	7.72775, 80.26457	04.01.2019
06	Thorayaya	Bridge	Deduru Oya	7.52101, 80.42811	15.02.2019

6 Deviation from Work Plan

Installation of twenty-seven (27) 4nse weather stations in Deduru Oya basin was commenced on 06th March 2018 and completed on 21st July 2018. The installation process has been delayed due to the following reasons:

- 1) All the universities in Sri Lanka had to close for several weeks in year 2017 and 2018 due to the trade union actions launched by Non-Academic university staff. This influenced for interruption of weather station development activities and as well as deployment activities.
- 2) A considerable time was taken for getting electronic items purchased from the international market such as Davis rain collector, temperature sensor, wind direction sensor, wind speed sensor, UV-IR sensor, BME sensor and water level sensor.
- 3) As per the university financial regulations, the maximum advance money which can be requested by any permanent staff member in the university is limited to LKR 100,000 (approximately USD 550). Therefore, the items were purchased in small quantities at several times. This was also delayed the system development and deployment process.
- 4) Due to the delay in buying electronic items in small quantities and due to the higher shipping cost and financial restrictions imposed by UOM, it was decided to buy all the rain gauges required for the stations at once through SUPSI. However, when clearing the imported rain gauges from the Sri Lankan Customs, it took considerable time since it involves getting permission from the ministry of finance as well as from the higher education ministry.

- 5) Some of the electronic items (solar panels, BMEs and some related parts) which were purchased from the local market got delayed during the Chinese New Year period, since the vendors in the local market imported them from China.
- 6) Some stations had to relocate to new locations after completing the installation. The MOD station which was installed at the Lyceum Adventure Park was originally located at the Irrigation Department of Kurunegala. However, due to some construction activities in the Irrigation Department, the station had to relocate to Lyceum Adventure Park, which is in the same sub-basin, 2 ½ km away from the Irrigation Department. The PCB station at Kedapathwehera School, was relocated to a different location at the school premises, due to some construction activities.

7 Conclusion

Under the 4onse research project, thirty-two (32) weather stations and six (06) river gauges have been installed in Sri Lanka. Out of the thirty-two (32) weather stations, twenty seven (27) have been installed in the Deduru Oya basin and two (02) stations have been installed outside the basin, in areas called Lankapura and Walapane. The remaining three (03) stations have been installed in University of Moratuwa for testing purposes. Table 7 shows the summary of the installed locations.

Table 7: Summary of the locations where 4onse systems have been installed

Location type	Number	Remarks
Schools	21	Located inside the Deduru Oya basin
Temples	01	
Locations belong to Irrigation Department	03	
Other locations – Bathalagoda Rice Research Institute, Lyceum Adventure Park	02	
Divisional Secretariat Offices	02	Located outside the Deduru Oya basin
University of Moratuwa	03	Located at University of Moratuwa for testing purposes

The process of determining the optimum locations for the stations in Deduru Oya basin started with discretizing the watershed into sub-basins. Locations were identified primarily based on the precipitation. Satellite retrieved weather data was applied in Shannon’s Entropy method to measure the spatial distribution of uncertainty levels of precipitation. In addition, requirements of the hydrological modeling software and several other factors were considered in determining the number and the locations for the stations.

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